

Variational approach to photonic quantum circuits via the parameter shift rule

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In the era of noisy intermediate-scale quantum computers, variational quantum algorithms are promising approaches for solving optimization tasks by training parameterized quantum circuits with the aid of classical routines informed by quantum measurements. In this context, photonic platforms based on reconfigurable integrated optics are an ideal candidate for implementing these algorithms. Among various techniques to train variational circuits, the parameter shift rule enables the exact calculation of cost function derivatives efficiently, facilitating gradient descent-based optimization. In this paper, we derive a formulation of the parameter shift rule for computing derivatives and integrals tailored to reconfigurable optical linear circuits and based on the Boson Sampling paradigm. This allows us to naturally embed common types of experimental noise, such as partial distinguishability and mixedness of the states, thus obtaining a resilient approach. Finally, we employ the developed approach to experimentally test variational algorithms with single-photon states processed in a reconfigurable six-mode universal integrated interferometer. Specifically, we apply the photonic parameter shift rules to the variational implementation, on a photonic platform, of both an eigensolver and a Universal-NOT gate.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the current era of noisy quantum devices on an intermediate scale (NISQ), variational quantum algorithms (VQA) represent one of the main strategies to overcome some of the technical challenges implied by the use of noisy quantum processors. In fact, VQA opens up the possibility of applying current quantum devices to relevant applications [1,2]. These algorithms are based on the application of a hybrid quantum-classical approach. In the context of VQAs, a particular quantum or classical problem is encoded in a cost function whose minima represent the desired solution of the problem, which can be efficiently evaluated via measurements carried out at the output of a parametric quantum circuit. In this way, a classical optimizer can be employed to iteratively tune the parameters of the quantum circuit in order to minimize the cost function and thus find the desired optimal solution [see Fig. 1(a)]. This type of algorithm has been successfully applied to several different tasks, such as quantum dynamics simulation [3,4], quantum chemistry [5,6], variational eigensolvers [7–9], quantum cloning machines [10], quantum metrology [11], and optimization of quantum

algorithms [12–14]. In the context of photon-based quantum computation, reconfigurable integrated circuits do represent one of the main platforms which can be used to implement and test VQAs, as they allow for the realization of relatively complex linear optical interferometers with a large number of adaptive parameters while maintaining a high degree of stability and compactness [15–17].

One of the principal challenges of the VQA is the application of the classical optimizer to the quantum circuit. Indeed, many classical optimization algorithms are based on the estimation of the cost function gradient through the use of the finite difference method, in which derivatives are replaced by differences between function evaluations at nearby points that are distant by a small amount $\varepsilon \ll 1$. While for numerical algorithms fully running on classical hardware this is a feasible approach, such a task becomes impractical in the case of noisy quantum devices. Indeed, in the latter case it is necessary to find a value of ε small enough to provide a good approximation of the derivative while being at the same time large enough so that the signal-to-noise ratio of the derivative estimation is small. One of the possible solutions to solve such an intrinsic problem of derivatives calculations is given by the use of gradient-free optimization algorithms. Here only the comparison of the function value at relatively distant points and a heuristic on how to search the minimum are required. Many experimental implementations of VQAs in photonic platforms which can be found in the literature have relied on such gradient-free approaches [8–10,18,19].

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FIG. 1. Variational quantum circuits and the photonic parameter shift rule. (a) A variational quantum circuit is a quantum device that takes in input a quantum register of qubits ρ which evolves through a parametric unitary transformation $U(\vec{\theta})$. The measurement outcomes on the output states fed a classical gradient-free or gradient-based optimization routine to change the parameters of the circuit and minimize a particular cost function. (b) The photonic version replaces the variational circuit with a multiport parametric interferometer in which N photons evolve. The output photon distribution depends on the internal phases of the optical circuit (green and red rectangles) through trigonometric functions. This makes it feasible for the circuit to estimate both the value and the gradient of such a class of functions via the parameter shift rule. In the figure we display the six-mode universal integrated interferometer used for testing the method in one- and two-photon experiments.

In the circuit-based quantum computing paradigm a different solution has been developed, known as the *parameter shift rule* [20–22]. This method provides an unbiased estimation of the derivatives of a function, i.e., without approximations, by evaluating the function on a set of distant points and thus enabling the evaluation of derivatives on noisy quantum hardware. This is possible since it can be shown that the output probabilities of a quantum circuit are trigonometric functions of the variational parameters, thus allowing the calculation of derivatives by evaluating the functions at points that are distant multiples of π . While the parameter shift rule has already been developed in a circuit-based approach, its translation to a photonic scenario poses some challenges and is in principle associated to additional overheads in terms of number of ancillary modes and photons. This motivates the need to derive a general parameter shift rule that is conceived to operate natively for photonic systems. A first approach to the parameter shift rule for photonic architectures can be found in Ref. [11], and similar results were found in [23] applied to the expressiveness of photonic circuits for machine learning applications.

In this paper, we derive a general photonic version of the parameter shift rule applied to linear optical circuits using the Boson Sampling formalism [24] that allows us to incorporate

the typical sources of noise of a multi-photon experiment into the derivation. We experimentally test this approach in a universal integrated optical chip. The photonic parameter shift rule is employed for the calculation of gradients and integrals in order to apply gradient-based optimization algorithms directly on the quantum hardware. In particular, we apply such a strategy to a classical minimization problem known as variational eigensolver [25]. Analogously, the same method is applied to a notorious problem in quantum information known as the optimal Universal-NOT gate [26–28].

The structure of the work is the following. In Sec. II the theory behind the parameter shift is presented by deriving the analogous version for linear photonic circuits. Specifically, it is demonstrated that the probability of an event at an interferometer’s output as its phases change takes the shape of a trigonometric series, the degree of which is proportional to the number of photons in the circuit. This makes it possible to derive parameter shift rules analogous to those developed for quantum circuits. It is also shown that the main sources of noise in photonic experiments, such as partial photon distinguishability and losses, do not affect the functional form and thus the application of the parameter shift rule remains robust. In addition, it is shown how the theory behind the parameter shift rule can also be extended to the calculation of integrals over some of the parameters of the circuit. In Sec. III we experimentally test the developed theory using one and two photons in a six-mode reconfigurable photonic circuit. First, a three-mode interferometer is used to show how the parameter shift rule changes as the structure of the interferometer and the number of photons used vary. Subsequently, applications to compute derivatives and integrals are used to solve two variational problems, specifically, a variational eigensolver and a variational Universal-NOT (U-NOT) gate. Finally, in Sec. IV we present a summary of the results covered and an overview of the future prospects.

II. PARAMETER SHIFT RULE FOR LINEAR PHOTONIC CIRCUIT

For the computation of the gradient of a cost function defined through a parametric quantum device, one of the most established ideas is to use the so-called parameter shift rule [22], whose purpose is to exactly and efficiently measure the derivative of a function by evaluating the function itself at shifted points “far” from each other.

The idea behind the method is that for a large variety of quantum circuits, the dependence of the measurement output probabilities on the variational parameters can be expressed as a finite Fourier series.

In particular, for most cases the expression can be further simplified by noting that the angular frequencies are integer, meaning that in general one can write the output probabilities as

$$f(x) = a_0 + \sum_{l=1}^R a_l \cos(lx) + b_l \sin(lx). \quad (1)$$

Due to this functional form, we can reconstruct the function by evaluating it in $2R + 1$ points. This can be related to the trigonometric interpolation problem [29].

Moreover, its derivative $f'(x_0)$ in a given point x_0 can be evaluated by following the approach of Ref. [22].

Parameter shift rule: *Given a function $f(x)$ in the form of Eq. (1), the derivative of the function in a point x_0 can be computed by evaluating the function in a set of $2R$ translated points $x_0 + x_k$ with $\{x_k = \frac{2k+1}{2R}\pi | k \in \{0, \dots, 2R-1\}\}$, using the formula*

$$\left. \frac{df}{dx} \right|_{x=x_0} = \sum_{k=0}^{2R-1} f\left(x_0 + \frac{2k+1}{2R}\pi\right) \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{4R \sin^2\left(\frac{2k+1}{4R}\pi\right)}. \quad (2)$$

For more specific details, we refer to the specialized literature [22].

A. Photonic phase

Now we show how the parameter shift rule behaves in the photonic framework, specifically when considering the linear optical model comprising single-photon resources interacting in a multimode interferometer composed of linear optical elements [30]. We consider N indistinguishable photons at the input of a linear m -mode interferometer described by the unitary matrix U , which defines the transformation between input and output mode operators as $b_j^\dagger = \sum_k U_{jk} a_k^\dagger$. Such a unitary matrix U admits in general a decomposition in terms of a set of single-mode phase shifts and balanced two-mode beam splitters, as described in Ref. [31]. Thus, any output probability will in general be a function of a set of single-mode phase shifts φ .

Within the linear optical framework, the input distribution of the photons is defined by the mode occupation list $\vec{r} = (r_1, \dots, r_m)$, where r_j photons are in the input mode j . Similarly, we can define the set of output states as $\vec{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_m)$. For convenience, we define the mode assignment list [32] as

$$\vec{d}(\vec{r}) = (\underbrace{1, \dots, 1}_{r_1}, \underbrace{2, \dots, 2}_{r_2}, \dots, \underbrace{m, \dots, m}_{r_m}). \quad (3)$$

We also define the normalization constant $\mu(\vec{r}) = \prod_{j=1}^m r_j!$. Finally, we define the scattering matrix M associated with the input and output states \vec{r} and \vec{s} as the $N \times N$ matrix, defined as

$$M_{hj} = U_{\vec{d}(\vec{s})_h, \vec{d}(\vec{r})_j}. \quad (4)$$

The probability to obtain the output state \vec{s} from the input state \vec{r} can be computed as [33]

$$P(\vec{s}|\vec{r}) = \frac{|\text{Per}(M)|^2}{\mu(\vec{r})\mu(\vec{s})}, \quad (5)$$

where $\text{Per}(M)$ is the permanent of the scattering matrix M .

We now discuss the scenario in which the unitary evolution $U(\varphi)$ of the interferometer depends on a single phase shift φ , and we prove that the probability function of Eq. (5) can be written in the functional form of Eq. (1).

In general the unitary transformation $U(\varphi)$ can be divided into three parts,

$$U(\varphi) = U^{(2)}\Phi^{(r)}U^{(1)}, \quad (6)$$

where $U^{(1)}$ and $U^{(2)}$ are unitary matrices describing the linear interferometer before and after the phase under exam and $\Phi^{(r)}$ is the unitary matrix of the phase φ in the mode r that can

be expressed as $\Phi_{hj}^{(r)} = \delta_{hj} e^{i\delta_{hr}\varphi}$, where δ_{hj} is the Kronecker delta. Through this decomposition, it can be easily shown that each element of the unitary transformation is in the functional form:

$$U_{hj}(\varphi) = \sum_k U_{hk}^{(2)} U_{kj}^{(1)} e^{i\delta_{kr}\varphi} := c_{hj} + d_{hj} e^{i\varphi}. \quad (7)$$

Using the definition of the permanent, we can expand the formula for the probability shown in Eq. (5) as

$$P(\vec{s}|\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{\mu(\vec{r})\mu(\vec{s})} \left| \sum_{\sigma \in S_N} \prod_{k=1}^N U_{\sigma(\vec{d}(\vec{s})_k), \vec{d}(\vec{r})_k} \right|^2, \quad (8)$$

where S_N is the set of permutations of N elements. Given the functional form in Eq. (7) of the coefficient of the unitary matrix, and since the product of N binomial terms of degree 1 is a polynomial with degree N , we can write

$$\sum_{\sigma \in S_N} \prod_{k=1}^N U_{\sigma(\vec{d}(\vec{s})_k), \vec{d}(\vec{r})_k} = \sum_{k=0}^N c_k e^{ik\varphi}. \quad (9)$$

This gives us the final result

$$P(\vec{s}|\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{\mu(\vec{r})\mu(\vec{s})} \sum_{k=0}^N d_k e^{ik\varphi} + d_k^* e^{-ik\varphi}, \quad (10)$$

where $d_k = \sum_{h=0}^{N-h} c_h^* c_{h+k}$. This equality can be rewritten as

$$P(\vec{s}|\vec{r}) = \sum_{k=0}^N a_k \cos(k\varphi) + b_k \sin(k\varphi), \quad (11)$$

proving that the output probabilities from a linear interferometer follow the functional form of Eq. (1) with $R = N$, i.e., equal to the number of photons at the input of the interferometer.

When the variational parameters are associated with more than one phase, the result is similar. The functional form is a multiparameter Fourier series of degree N in each of the phase variables. The demonstration is identical to the single-parameter case. For example, in the case of two phases φ_1 and φ_2 , the output probability will be a Fourier series in the first phase φ_1 as in Eq. (11), whose coefficients $a_k(\varphi_2)$ and $b_k(\varphi_2)$ are themselves Fourier series in the second phase φ_2 .

B. Role of experimental noise

Notably, if one relaxes the assumptions of full indistinguishability of the photonic resources and considers a generic input state that includes mixed states and partial distinguishability in the photon's internal degrees of freedom, the functional form shown in Eq. (11) does not change. To prove this, we employ the formalism presented in Ref. [34]. There it

is shown that the transition probabilities can be computed as

$$P(\vec{s}|\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{\mu(\vec{r})\mu(\vec{s})} \sum_{\sigma_1 \in \mathcal{S}_N} \sum_{\sigma_2 \in \mathcal{S}_N} J(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \times \prod_{k=1}^N U_{\sigma_1(\vec{s})_k, \vec{d}(\vec{r})_k}^* \prod_{h=1}^N U_{\sigma_2(\vec{d}(\vec{s})_h), \vec{d}(\vec{r})_h}, \quad (12)$$

where $J(\sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ is the spatial distinguishability matrix, which is a Hermitian positive semidefinite matrix indexed by two permutations σ_1 and σ_2 that takes into account not only the partial distinguishability of the photon but also the photon states mixedness, the sensitivities of the output detectors, and, more generally, photon losses.

Using the same reasoning as in Eq. (9), we can write

$$\prod_{h=1}^N U_{\sigma(\vec{d}(\vec{s})_h), \vec{d}(\vec{r})_h} = \sum_{k=0}^N c_k^{(\sigma)} e^{ik\varphi}. \quad (13)$$

Using the fact that J is a Hermitian matrix, one can show that Eq. (10) with coefficients d_k will be now given as

$$d_k = \sum_{h=0}^{N-k} \sum_{\sigma_1 \in \mathcal{S}_N} \sum_{\sigma_2 \in \mathcal{S}_N} J(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) c_h^{*(\sigma_1)} c_{h+k}^{(\sigma_2)}. \quad (14)$$

Thus, analytically, the transition probabilities at the output of a linear interferometer can always be expressed in terms of a Fourier expansion as in Eq. (1), irrespective of the indistinguishability properties of the input photons.

Furthermore, we note that the value of the parameter R of Eq. (1) in the photonic picture is not strictly related to the number of photons at the input of the interferometer itself but to the maximum number of photons that can interact with a considered phase, given the input-output Fock-state configuration. This, in turn, makes it possible to decrease the number of measurements required, depending on the structure of the interferometer and the input and output configurations considered. A complete proof of this behavior is reported in Appendix A.

C. Beyond derivatives computation

Until now, we have described a method to compute the derivatives of a function with the parameter shift rule. However, the knowledge of the functional form of Eq. (1) allows us to extend this method to different kinds of computations. As an example, some cost functions in variational algorithm scenarios involve the average over a set of states that can be encoded in one or more parameters of the variational circuit [35]. This problem can be translated into the calculation of the integral of the function $f(x)$ weighted with a periodic distribution $g(x)$,

$$M = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx f(x) g(x), \quad (15)$$

if we define the parameters

$$c_k = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx g(x) \frac{\sin\left(\frac{2R+1}{2}x\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{x}{2} - \frac{k}{2R+1}\pi\right)}, \quad (16)$$

and then the integral can be rewritten as

$$M = \sum_{k=0}^{2R} \frac{(-1)^k c_k}{2R+1} f\left(\frac{2k}{2R+1}\pi\right). \quad (17)$$

In general, this requires $2R+1$ evaluations of the function $f(x)$. However, if additional information on the parity of the weight distribution $g(x)$ is available, then one can reduce the number of measurements to $2R$. Indeed, as an example, if we want to compute the average of the function $\langle f(x) \rangle$ [i.e., $g(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi}$], we can use the following equation:

$$\langle f(x) \rangle = \frac{1}{2R} \sum_{k=0}^{2R-1} f\left(\frac{k\pi}{R}\right). \quad (18)$$

As a relevant aspect, we observe that there are no approximations in the derivation. This implies that the error is only due to the evaluation of the function $f(x)$ and not to the use of a finite sample for the evaluation of the mean.

The formal derivation of the results given in this section and the generalization of the formulas for a generic distribution $g(x)$ are given in Appendix B.

III. EXPERIMENTAL IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we will show how the derivative estimation rules described in the previous section can be applied to an actual implementation of a variational circuit in a photonic platform. Specifically, we tested the effectiveness of the parameter shift rule in a quantum photonic experiment by exploiting pairs of indistinguishable single-photon states and a six-mode programmable universal integrated photonic circuit. Before going into the details of the results, we briefly describe the experimental platform.

The single-photon source is a parametric down-conversion based on a beta-barium-borate nonlinear crystal. The source generates photon pairs at $\lambda = 785$ nm. Spectral filtering, time synchronization, and polarization control over the two-photon states allowed us to reach a level of indistinguishability up to 0.99 ± 0.01 . The two photons are coupled through single-mode fibers to a six-mode integrated optical circuit. The architecture of the device follows the universal scheme of Ref. [31] pictured in Fig. 1(b). Each red and green square represents a tunable phase of the interferometer, while each crossing stands for an unbiased beam splitter. The interferometer can be programmed by changing the internal phase values to perform any unitary transformation over the optical modes. The chip is fabricated through the femtosecond-laser-writing technology [36]. A set of 30 heaters that induce local changes in the refractive index of the waveguides by the thermal-optic effect enables the full reconfigurability of the internal phases. Further details on the performance and specs of such an integrated device can be found in Refs. [10,37,38]. Finally, a multimode fiber array collects the two photons in the outputs and sends the signal to avalanche photodiode single-photon detectors. A time-to-digital converter device processes twofold coincidences among the detectors.

The whole platform is controlled by a classical routine fed by the function values and gradient, computed by the parameter shift rule, both estimated from the photon counts.

FIG. 2. Parameter shift rule in a three-mode interferometer. (a) Universal three-mode interferometer inside the six-mode one. In orange are the variational phases where the parameter shift rule is tested. (b) Two-photon counts for $C_{110}(\theta_2)$ (blue), $C_{110}(\theta_1)$ (purple), and $C_{011}(\theta_3)$ (green) by varying the respective angle in $[0, 2\pi]$. (c) One- and two-photon rules applied for estimating the averages of the twofold coincidences $\langle C_{110}(\theta_2) \rangle$, $\langle C_{110}(\theta_1) \rangle$ and $\langle C_{011}(\theta_3) \rangle$. In red the experimental estimates of the one-photon rule, in orange the two-photon rule results, and in blue the theoretical expectation. In (d) the partial derivative with respect to θ_2 computed via the one-photon rule (red) and the two-photon rule (orange). The solid blue line in (b) is the fit of the data and the one in (d) is its partial derivative. (e)–(f) Partial derivatives $\frac{\partial C_{110}}{\partial \theta_2}$ and $\frac{\partial C_{011}}{\partial \theta_3}$ computed via the two rules parameters. In both cases, the two estimates are compatible within the experimental uncertainties due to the Poisson statistics of single-photon counts. The solid lines are the theoretical expectation for the partial derivative.

Then, the variational algorithm works as follows. In order to compute the gradient of a cost function which is related to the output parameters of the circuits, the rule presented in Eq. (2) requires shifting the variational phases of the interferometer [in orange in Fig. 1(b)] of a given amount. To this end, the phases of the chip under analysis can be suitably programmed to perform such a task, the collection of single-photon counts and the output two-photon distribution give an estimate of both the function and of its partial derivatives. Then, a gradient-based optimization performed by a classical routine iteratively updates the on-circuit variational parameters and predicts their optimal values for the problem under investigation.

A. Testing one- and two-photon rules

This preliminary section aims to provide insight into the operation and effectiveness of a N -photon parameter shift rule that follows from Eq. (2) with $R = N$. In particular, we focus on the verification of one- and two-photon rules by sending two indistinguishable photons from the source to the integrated interferometer. We select a portion of the six-mode circuit that implements a three-mode transformation, and we inject the photons in the input configurations $[1, 0, 1]$, where the string expresses that the two photons are injected from modes 1 and 3 [see Fig. 2(a)].

The structure of the interferometer is the ideal test bed to understand how the N -photon rule works. The transition function that links the input string to the photon counts in one

of the outputs $\{[1, 1, 0], [1, 0, 1], [0, 1, 1]\}$ is in the form of Eq. (1) and depends in general on the three phases highlighted in orange in Fig. 2(a), so that in general $f = f(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$. In particular, we consider the functions $C_{110}(\theta_2)$, $C_{110}(\theta_1)$, and $C_{011}(\theta_3)$, where $C_{ijk}(\theta)$ correspond to the two-photon coincidence counts for two photons exiting from the output configuration $[i, j, k]$, while the angles in the parentheses are the phases varied in the application of the parameter shift rule [see Fig. 2(b)]. We expect from the previous derivation that the n -photon rule with N equal to the number of photons in the circuit, in our case $N = 2$, always works in order to estimate both the function averages and partial derivatives. However, the structure of the circuit and the presence of possible symmetries could allow use of a simplified photon rule that involves a lower number of photons. We discuss in detail such an intuition.

In Fig. 2(c) we test the two-photon and the one-photon rules for the estimation of the three averages $\langle C_{110}(\theta_2) \rangle$, $\langle C_{110}(\theta_1) \rangle$, and $\langle C_{011}(\theta_3) \rangle$. The estimation of $\langle C_{110}(\theta_2) \rangle$ is one of the cases that requires the use of the two-photon rule for a correct computation. In fact, the estimation via the one-photon rule does not provide a correct estimate of the average. In contrast, if one looks at the phase θ_1 in the photonic circuit, it is evident that only one of the two photons interacts with such a phase. This means that in principle the one-photon rule could be enough for the estimation of $\langle C_{110}(\theta_1) \rangle$. To prove this, we compare the average of this function computed through the two rules. Indeed, with respect to $\langle C_{110}(\theta_1) \rangle$, the one-photon rule's estimate is compatible with the two-photon

rule's estimate, within the experimental errors. Furthermore, both estimations are in accordance with the expected theoretical values. Such a result confirms the effectiveness of the simplified rule that involves only one photon for some parameters and functions. A similar reasoning holds for the third average $\langle C_{011}(\theta_3) \rangle$. Indeed, this is another configuration in which only one photon is sensitive to changes in the parameter. Specifically, while the input state would allow in principle the interaction of two photons with the parameter θ_3 , the transition probability that links the input to the output $[0, 1, 1]$ has only one photon interacting with θ_3 . This allows us to use the one-photon rule. The rightmost panel of Fig. 2(c) shows the estimates of $\langle C_{011}(\theta_3) \rangle$ with the two rules and their accordance with the expectation.

We now move to the verification of the photonic parameter shift rule to compute the partial derivatives of a function $f = f(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$. Specifically, here we are interested in the computation of $\frac{\partial C_{110}}{\partial \theta_2}$, $\frac{\partial C_{110}}{\partial \theta_1}$, and $\frac{\partial C_{011}}{\partial \theta_3}$. As a first test, we report in Fig. 2(b) the two-photon counts $C_{110}(\theta_2)$ collected by varying the parameter θ_2 in $[0, 2\pi]$ and keeping constant the others. In Fig. 2(d) we show the partial derivative according to the one- and two-photon rules. We retrieve a similar behavior as the one probed in the previous investigation, only by employing the two-photon rule one can compute a correct estimate for the derivative, in accordance with the theoretical curve obtained by computing the analytical derivative of the data fit shown in Fig. 2(b). Finally, the experimental estimates $\frac{\partial C_{110}}{\partial \theta_1}$ and $\frac{\partial C_{011}}{\partial \theta_3}$ via the two- and one-photon rules are also shown. Again, for these configurations the one-photon rule is sufficient for obtaining the correct computation of the partial derivatives, whose two estimates appear to be in accordance with the theoretical derivatives.

Such a first experimental investigation demonstrates that the quantum variational circuit can be controlled suitably in order to calculate trigonometric functions and their partial derivatives, directly on a device. Furthermore, it shows that the symmetries and structure of a given circuit can simplify the calculation by enabling the estimation of a function gradient via a lower-order parameter shift rule. This property could become significant in large-scale experimental implementations, since it would reduce the number of necessary measurements for given function integrals and gradient estimations.

B. Variational eigensolver

After proving experimentally that the parameter shift rule, applied to a photonic test bed, correctly predicts derivatives of transition functions at the output of a linear optical interferometer, the natural next step is to variationally solve a practical problem by computing the gradients of the relevant cost function fully on-device. Recently, such a problem of computing gradients with linear optical circuits via the parameter shift rule has been investigated to directly compute the so-called Fisher information in the context of quantum metrology [11]. In our case we employ the knowledge of the gradient of a function to implement a variational approximation protocol in order to compute the ground-state energy of a hydrogen molecule (H_2).

Specifically, recall that the molecule bond energy depends on the nuclear separation between the two atoms. To

TABLE I. Coefficient of the hydrogen molecule Hamiltonian. Parameters of the two-qubit Hamiltonian operator for a nuclear separation of $r = 0.7414 \text{ \AA}$ between the two atoms. All the values are reported in Hartree energy units (Ha).

α	β	γ	δ	μ
-0.340	0.394	0.394	0.011	-0.181

obtain the expected minimal energy for each separation length, the OpenFermion package provided the data and calculations [39]. The minimum ground-state energy is found at the known bond length of an H_2 molecule: $r = 0.7414 \text{ \AA}$. Then, we can compute the Hamiltonian of an H_2 molecule at such a length using OpenFermion, which gives the Hamiltonian in the form of a fermionic operator. The binary code function can then transform this operator into a qubit operator with lower qubit requirements, i.e., using two qubits instead of four. Thus, the Hamiltonian can be described by a sum of tensor products of single-qubit Pauli operators:

$$H_{qubit} = \alpha II + \beta ZI + \gamma IZ + \delta ZZ + \mu XX, \quad (19)$$

with coefficients that depend on the bond length. The values of the coefficients for an atomic separation equal to $r = 0.7414 \text{ \AA}$ are reported in Table I.

The ground state of the molecule has an energy E_0 such that for any other state $E_0 \leq \langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle$. To find the ground state, one can therefore minimize $\langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle$ by making $\Psi(\theta_i)$ vary.

Previous variational approaches to similar problems via photonic integrated circuits [7,9] employed a gradient-free classical optimization routine, such as the Nelder-Mead optimization [40], with solely the expectation value of the energy computed by the quantum hardware. In particular, these experiments considered two dual-rail encoded qubits, single-qubit rotations, and a probabilistic entangling photonic CNOT gate to implement the variational searching of the ground-state energy of a molecular compound. Here we apply the introduced photonic parameter shift rule and perform the variational optimization via a gradient-based algorithm, with functional gradients directly computed on-device. Specifically, we encode the variational eigensolver in a general four-mode interferometer and use the circuit depth of the whole six-mode device.

In our experiment, two indistinguishable photons enter inputs 3 and 5 of the six-mode chip and undergo a four-mode unitary transformation [blue area in Fig. 3(a)] which gives $|\Psi\rangle$. In fact, each photon encodes a dual-rail qubit in which the logical states correspond to the presence of the photon in one of the two paths. The blue area of the circuit can implement any four-mode transformation by properly programming the nine internal phases highlighted in orange. Then $\langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle$ is computed by measuring the expectation values associated to the Pauli operators of each term of Eq. (19) (see Appendix D for more details). Before measuring the XX product, we change the basis from ZZ to XX using a tunable Mach-Zehnder interferometer on each qubit [yellow region in Fig. 3(a)]. All the other products share the same basis and are thus measured at once, so each computation of $\langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle$ takes two measurements (see Appendix D). For

FIG. 3. Photonic variational eigensolver. (a) Structure of the variational circuit for evaluating the ground-state energy of H2. Two dual-rail qubits are encoded in the two photons injected in modes 3 and 5 of the six-mode interferometer. Then, we have a universal four-mode interferometer that allows us to generate the ground state of the Hamiltonian (blue part of the circuit). The orange rectangles highlight the nine variational phases. The last layer in yellow encodes the measurements of the operators X and Z on each qubit. (b) Trend of the ground-state energy value during the minimization by the BFGS method. The algorithm is fed by the gradient calculated by the quantum variational circuit via the two-photon parameter shift rule.

the minimization, we use the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) gradient-based optimization method [41] on $\langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle$, with nine variational phases represented by orange rectangles Fig. 3(a) and the gradient given by the two-photons rule. The gradient computed by the quantum circuit at each iteration enters into the standard *minimize* function of the Python Scipy package [42].

In Fig. 3(b) we report the results of the minimization process. Here, the dots represent the values of the energy during the optimization process as a function of the number of iterations of the minimization protocol. The final result is $E_{\text{exp}} = -1.150 \pm 0.012$ Ha, compatible with the theoretical value of $E_{\text{th}} = -1.137$ Ha (orange line). Moreover, for comparison, we simulate the experiment 1000 times, with comparable finite statistics, and we plot a standard deviation around the average (blue region). Via this experiment, we show the possibility of applying the parameter shift rule in a photonic quantum computation paradigm in order to compute the gradients of a suitably defined cost function computed by the evaluation of probabilities at the output of a linear optical interferometer. This, in turn, enables us to use an efficient gradient-based optimization algorithm in order to variationally optimize such a cost function, thus unlocking the capability of running a large array of variational algorithms fully on-device.

C. Variational implementation of a Universal-NOT gate

Finally, we present an application where the parameter shift rule is applied to compute the cost function as an average over a continuous set of states and the gradient of the cost function. In particular, we implement an optimal U-NOT gate [26–28] with a variational circuit.

A U-NOT gate is defined as a gate that transforms a qubit in a particular state $|\psi\rangle = \cos(\theta/2)e^{i\phi}|0\rangle + \sin(\theta/2)|1\rangle$ into the orthogonal one $|\psi^\perp\rangle = \sin(\theta/2)e^{i\phi}|0\rangle - \cos(\theta/2)|1\rangle$. Since the transformation is not unitary, it cannot be implemented deterministically; however, it is possible to create an approximate U-NOT gate. In literature, a concept of *optimal* U-NOT gate has been defined as the unitary transformation which has the maximal average fidelity over all the possible input states. In Ref. [26] they show that the maximal average fidelity achievable quantum mechanically is $F_{\text{U-NOT}} = 2/3$.

To provide a variational implementation of an optimal U-NOT gate, we use a universal three-mode interferometer inside the six-mode one, where the qubit is encoded with a dual-rail encoding in the first two modes of the interferometer, and the output state is postselected on the condition that no photon is measured at the output of the third mode [see Fig. 4(a)]. To train the circuit we chose as input a state defined by the two angles $|\Psi(\theta_p, \phi_p)\rangle$ and we directly measure the output state fidelity by projecting the final dual-rail encoded state on the expected orthogonal output state $|\Psi^\perp(\theta_p, \phi_p)\rangle$. The cost function employed to train the circuit is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} S(\vec{\theta}) &= - \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{4\pi} F(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}) P_s(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}) \\ &= - \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{4\pi} P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $F(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta})$ is the fidelity, $P_s(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta})$ is the success probability of the protocol, $P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta})$ is the probability that the photon came out from the first mode after the projection that is exactly the product of the previous two, and $\vec{\theta}$ are the variational parameters of the U-NOT circuit. The proposed cost function is designed to maximize the output fidelity, favoring the states with a higher success probability. Such an average over the Bloch sphere can be estimated through the parameter shift rule for the integrals. In particular, we found that the calculation of the cost function is equivalent to estimate $S(\vec{\theta})$ as

$$S(\vec{\theta}) = -\frac{1}{6} \sum_{(i,j) \in Q} P_1(i, j, \vec{\theta}), \quad (21)$$

where Q is a set of six pairs of angles (θ_p, ϕ_p) . More precisely, $Q = \{(0, 0), (\frac{\pi}{2}, 0), (\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}), (\frac{\pi}{2}, \pi), (\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{2}), (\pi, 0)\}$. The complete derivation is presented in Appendix E.

We then move to the experimental minimization of the cost function that is performed via the one-photon rule in the six-mode photonic chip. The circuit is programmed as in Fig. 4(a), where the phases $\vec{\theta} = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_5\}$ are the variational phases; the blue and the purple phases are those used for the preparation and the projection on the orthogonal state. The minimization process follows the same procedure as the

FIG. 4. Photonic U-NOT. (a) Structure of the variational circuit for the implementation of an optimal U-NOT gate. A dual-rail qubit is prepared by injecting a photon in a tunable beam splitter controlled by the phases (θ_p, ϕ_p) (red part of the circuit). After that, the state is injected in a three-mode universal interferometer implementing the variational U-NOT gate controlled by the five phases $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_5$ (blue region). Finally, after postselecting on the condition that no photon exits from the third output, the state is projected on the orthogonal state $(\theta_m = \pi - \theta_p, \phi_m = \pi - \phi_p)$ and the fidelity is estimated by the resulting measurement. (b) Distribution of the fidelity of the states used for the validation process, in orange the theoretical distribution. In the inset we present the trend of the cost function during the minimization process with orange showing the theoretical minimum.

previous section. The quantum hardware computes the cost-function gradient that is fed into the minimization routine based on the BFGS method. This time the quantum circuit also computes the cost function.

The results are summarized in the inset of Fig. 4(b). The final result of the minimization is $S_f = -0.654 \pm 0.008$, which is compatible with a theoretical result of $S_f = -0.666$. To test the results we compute the average fidelity over a test set of 1000 qubit states uniformly sampled on the Bloch sphere. We obtained a result of $\langle F \rangle = 0.660 \pm 0.005$, which is compatible with the results of an optimal U-NOT gate $F_{\text{U-NOT}} = 2/3 = 0.666$. Furthermore, the accordance with the expectation is confirmed by the fidelity distributions reported in Fig. 4(b).

IV. DISCUSSION

In this work, we presented and experimentally validated an extension of the parameter shift rule typical of the circuit-based model of quantum computation to a photonic-based formalism. To this end, we showed that the functional relationship between the probabilities at the output of a linear optical interferometer and the internal phases that define an implemented unitary transformation can be expressed as a trigonometric series whose degree depends on the number of photons at the input of the interferometer. These results enable the theory of trigonometric interpolation to be applied in order to reconstruct the function, its derivative, and its integral by evaluating the function itself in a finite number of points uniformly distributed around a given point x_0 . Similar results for the computation of the gradient in a linear optical network are obtained in concurrent works [43,44] employing an alternative formalism compared to the present work. Moreover, with our formalism we showed that the main sources of noise in a photonic experiment such as losses and partial distinguishability and mixedness of the state do not affect the functional form of the observables. This allows us to apply the parameter shift rule without any particular change, even in noisy conditions or without the necessity of a full characterization of the photonic apparatus losses and source indistinguishability. We also demonstrated that it is possible to reduce the number of measurements required for such computations by exploiting the

regular geometry of a universal optical interferometer. Indeed, we proved that the degree of the trigonometric function is related to the number of photons propagating simultaneously through the phase under consideration.

The analytical theory developed here was then tested experimentally, exploiting a hybrid-photonic platform comprised of a spontaneous parametric down-conversion two-photon source and a six-mode, fully reconfigurable interferometer. In particular, we first validated the possibility of computing on-device both derivatives and integrals of cost functions, highlighting in the process how it is possible to reduce the number of measurements required using the information on the particular structure of the interferometer and on the relation between input and output state. Subsequently, the parameter shift rule was exploited to tackle two different variational optimization problems. In particular, we showed how the gradients computed via the parameter shift rule can feed a gradient-based classical optimization algorithm to implement a variational eigensolver. This allows us to iteratively find the optimal circuit parameters corresponding to a chosen task. Here, we demonstrated its functioning to estimate the ground-state energy of a hydrogen molecule. Then, we employed a similar approach to implement an optimal U-NOT gate on our photonic platform, achieving the maximum average fidelity expected within quantum mechanics via a variational approach.

Overall, we have shown the possibility of computing the derivative and the integral with respect to a parameter in an arbitrary linear optical interferometer. In contrast to previous proposals [45], the algorithm requires neither more photons nor more modes than those needed to evaluate the cost function. These results can be readily extended to more complex architectures, with a higher number of photons or optical modes, thus paving the way for further developments of efficient variational algorithms based on the use of reconfigurable integrated photonic circuits. As a future perspective, one can try to further optimize the algorithm by exploiting the geometry of the interferometer under consideration and using classically inspired techniques such as back-propagation, which have already found application in the circuit-based paradigm [46,47].

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting this study’s findings are available within the article.

APPENDIX A: MAXIMUM NUMBER REDUCTION

In this section, we demonstrate the relation between the number of photons that pass through the phase of interest and the degree of the trigonometric function that represents the probability of a particular input-output configuration.

Recovering the demonstration in the main text we can say that

$$U_{hj}(\varphi) = \sum_k U_{hk}^{(2)} U_{kj}^{(1)} e^{i\delta_{kr}\varphi} := c_{hj} + d_{hj} e^{i\varphi}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

However, by refining the reasoning, we can say that if there are no paths connecting the input j and the output h passing through the mode r , then the coefficient d_{hj} is null. This allows us to revise Eq. (13) of the main text,

$$\prod_{h=1}^N U_{\sigma(\vec{d}(\vec{s})_h), \vec{d}(\vec{r})_h} = \sum_{k=0}^{K_\sigma} c_k^{(\sigma)} e^{ik\varphi}, \quad (\text{A2})$$

with an upper bound of the degree of the equation not anymore N but a value $K_\sigma \leq N$ that counts the number of non-null coefficients d_{hj} , i.e., the maximum number of photons that can pass through the phase on mode r at the same time. Obviously, the upper bound K_σ depends both on the particular permutation σ considered and on the input and output states, omitted in the notation for readability reasons. Defined $K_M = \max_\sigma K_\sigma$, the maximum degree for all the possible permutations, i.e., the maximum number of photons that can pass through the phase at the same time, then the upper bound for Eqs. (14) and (10) instead of N became K_M , proving that

$$P(\vec{s} | \vec{r}) = \sum_{k=0}^{K_M} a_k \cos(k\varphi) + b_k \sin(k\varphi). \quad (\text{A3})$$

APPENDIX B: INTEGRAL COMPUTATION

In this section, we demonstrate the formula for the average of the functions. The goal is to compute the integral

$$M = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx f(x) g(x), \quad (\text{B1})$$

since the function $f(x)$ is a Fourier series of degree R . Then we can use the Dirichlet kernel [29] to rewrite the function as

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{2R} f\left(\frac{2k}{2R+1}\pi\right) \frac{(-1)^k}{2R+1} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{2R+1}{2}x\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{x}{2} - \frac{k}{2R+1}\pi\right)}. \quad (\text{B2})$$

The form of this equation gives us the final results presented in the main text.

1. Odd function

If the distribution function is odd, then we can rewrite the original integral as

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx \frac{f(x)g(x) + f(-x)g(-x)}{2} \\ &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx \frac{f(x) - f(-x)}{2} g(x), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B3})$$

where we can define $f_o(x)$ as the odd component of the function $f(x)$ as $f_o(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(-x)}{2}$. As previously done, we can rewrite the odd component of the function as [22]

$$f_o(x) = \sum_{k=1}^R f_o\left(\frac{2k-1}{2R}\pi\right) \frac{(-1)^k}{R} \frac{\cos(Rx) \sin(x)}{\cos\left(\frac{2k-1}{2R}\pi\right) - \cos(x)}, \quad (\text{B4})$$

so defining the coefficients

$$c_k = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx g(x) \frac{\cos(Rx) \sin(x)}{\cos\left(\frac{2k-1}{2R}\pi\right) - \cos(x)}, \quad (\text{B5})$$

and we can rewrite the original integral as

$$M = \sum_{k=1}^R \frac{c_k (-1)^k}{2R} \left[f\left(\frac{2k-1}{2R}\pi\right) - f\left(-\frac{2k-1}{2R}\pi\right) \right], \quad (\text{B6})$$

which requires $2R$ evaluation of the function $f(x)$ instead of $2R+1$ of the previous method.

2. Even functions

Similar to the previous case, if the distribution function is even then the integral can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx \frac{f(x)g(x) + f(-x)g(-x)}{2} \\ &= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx \frac{f(x) + f(-x)}{2} g(x), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B7})$$

defining $f_e(x)$ the even component of the function $f(x)$ as $f_e(x) = \frac{f(x) + f(-x)}{2}$. We can rewrite the function as [22]

$$f_e(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{2R-1} f\left(\frac{k\pi}{R}\right) \frac{(-1)^k}{2R} \frac{\sin(Rx) \sin(x)}{\cos\left(\frac{k\pi}{R}\right) - \cos(x)}, \quad (\text{B8})$$

defining

$$c_k = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} dx g(x) \frac{\sin(Rx) \sin(x)}{\cos\left(\frac{k\pi}{R}\right) - \cos(x)}. \quad (\text{B9})$$

This gives us the final expression for the original integral as

$$M = \sum_{k=0}^{2R-1} \frac{(-1)^k c_k}{2R} f\left(\frac{k\pi}{R}\right), \quad (\text{B10})$$

with the requirement of $2R$ evaluations of the function compared to the $2R+1$ of the initial method.

TABLE II. Average function evaluations. We report the average function evaluations for the training of a variational U-NOT gate using two different algorithms, namely, the BFGS and Nelder-Mead. The mean and the standard deviation are estimated over 10000 trials with a random starting point in the hypercube $[0, 2\pi]^n$ for different numbers of modes m and variational parameters n . Except for the first case where we use the interferometer depicted in Fig. 4(a) of the main text, we use the complete layout of Ref. [31] that has $n = m^2$.

Modes (m)	Parameters (n)	Average function evaluations	
		BFGS	Nelder-Mead
3	5	281 ± 66	254 ± 77
3	9	299 ± 97	347 ± 120
4	16	460 ± 150	560 ± 224
5	25	546 ± 181	674 ± 254
6	36	718 ± 233	867 ± 231

APPENDIX C: RESOURCE COMPARISON

In this section we provide a quantitative insight into the resources required by our algorithms compared to other algorithms employed in the literature.

First, we compare our algorithm with other one in the literature. The papers [43] and [44] derive the same technique discussed in this manuscript with a different approach and formalism. Overall, this means that our work and Refs. [43,44] are to be considered equivalent from both performance and a resource expenditure point of view. In contrast, in Ref. [45] the authors use a method that requires an interferometer of double the size compared to the one used to evaluate the cost function, and an additional photon. Moreover, the number of measurements scales quadratically with the number of modes, while in our approach they scale linearly with the number of photons at the input of the interferometer. In most cases, the number of photons is lower than the number of modes, meaning that our approach is more efficient in terms of the required measure.

Second, we want to compare the application of our algorithm in an optimization scenario. The comparison of gradient-based and gradient-free algorithms in terms of the required number of function evaluations is an open problem since it depends on the specific problem, in particular, on the number of parameters to be optimized, on the properties of the function, and on eventual bounds on the parameter space.

For example, let us consider the variational implementation of a U-NOT gate, which we present in Sec. III C. We can analyze the required number of function evaluations for the training of the variational circuit as a function of the size of the interferometer, i.e., the number of variational parameters in the interferometer. In particular, we compare the BFGS algorithm (the gradient-based algorithm used in the experiment) and the Nelder-Mead algorithm, which is the one typically chosen among the gradient-free methods. The results of this comparison are summarized in Table II, where the average function evaluation is estimated over 10000 trials with a random starting point in the hypercube $[0, 2\pi]^n$. As we can see, except for the case with $n = 5$ parameters, the use of the gradient-based algorithm is preferable. This shows that as the number of parameters increases, the gradient-based algorithm

seems preferable to the gradient-free case, demonstrating the potential of the algorithm proposed in the main text.

APPENDIX D: HAMILTONIAN MINIMIZATION PROTOCOL

For each measurement, two indistinguishable photons enter in modes 3 and 5 of the chip and undergo a four-mode unitary transformation which gives the state $|\Phi\rangle$. Then $\langle\Psi|H|\Psi\rangle$ is measured by measuring the probabilities of each term of Eq. (19) of the main text. Considering we are in the Z base for the two qubits, we can measure

$P(II)$	$P(ZI)$
$P_{13} + P_{14} + P_{23} + P_{24}$	$P_{13} - P_{14} + P_{23} - P_{24}$
$P(IZ)$	$P(ZZ)$
$P_{13} + P_{14} - P_{23} - P_{24}$	$P_{13} - P_{14} - P_{23} + P_{24}$

where

$$P_{ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{N_{13} + N_{14} + N_{23} + N_{24}}. \quad (D1)$$

By applying a basis change matrix from Z to X before the measurement, which in the chip is a $\pi/2$ beam splitter (red area in Fig. 3 of the main text), we can also measure $P(XX) = P_{13} - P_{14} - P_{23} + P_{24}$.

Note that the probability here is not the global probability of success but the probability postselected on the event that one photon is in the first two modes and the second photon in the last two modes, i.e., that we generate two proper qubits. Since the coincidences N_{ij} follow the two-photons rule, as they are proportional to the output probabilities, we can use the chain rule to compute the partial derivatives of the probabilities P_{ij} as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial P_{ij}}{\partial \theta_k} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k} \frac{N_{ij}}{N_{13} + N_{14} + N_{23} + N_{24}} \\ &= \frac{1}{S} \frac{\partial N_{ij}}{\partial \theta_k} + \frac{N_{ij}}{(S)^2} \frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta_k}, \end{aligned} \quad (D2)$$

where we define $S = N_{13} + N_{14} + N_{23} + N_{24}$, and every partial derivative of the counts is computed thanks to the two-photons rule:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_{ij}}{\partial \theta_k} &= \frac{2 + \sqrt{2}}{4} \left[N_{ij} \left(\theta_k + \frac{\pi}{4} \right) - N_{ij} \left(\theta_k - \frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{2 - \sqrt{2}}{4} \left[N_{ij} \left(\theta_k + \frac{3\pi}{4} \right) - N_{ij} \left(\theta_k - \frac{3\pi}{4} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (D3)$$

APPENDIX E: U-NOT COST FUNCTION

In this section, we show how to apply the parameter shift rule to compute the cost function of the U-NOT problem. We define $P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \theta_m, \phi_m, \bar{\theta})$ as the probability that the photon came out from the first mode of the interferometer as a function to the phases in the preparation stage and in the measurement stage, respectively. Due to the particular form of the

interferometer, the function presents some useful symmetries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1(2\pi - \theta_p, \phi_p, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p + \pi, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) \\
 P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, 2\pi - \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p + \pi, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) \\
 P_1(0, \phi_p, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(0, 0, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) \\
 P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, 0, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, 0, 0, \vec{\theta}) \\
 P_1(\pi, \phi_p, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(\pi, 0, \theta_m, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) \\
 P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \pi, \phi_m, \vec{\theta}) &= P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \pi, 0, \vec{\theta}). \quad (E1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Starting from the cost function,

$$S(\vec{\theta}) = - \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{4\pi} P_1(\theta, \phi, \pi - \theta, \pi - \phi, \vec{\theta}). \quad (E2)$$

Since only one photon is injected in the circuit, there is the probability P_1 is a trigonometric function of degree 1 in all four phases. However, since we control two phases simultaneously, this implies that in the variables θ_p and ϕ_p the probability function is a trigonometric function of degree 2 that for more clarity we write as $P_1(\theta, \phi, \vec{\theta}) = P_1(\theta, \phi, \pi - \theta, \pi - \phi, \vec{\theta})$. Now that we can find the value of R , we need to extend the integration over θ from $[0, \pi]$ to $[0, 2\pi]$. Using the symmetries and the periodicity of the function we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{2} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(\theta, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}) \\
 &= \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{2} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p + \pi, \vec{\theta}) \\
 &= \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{2} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(2\pi - \theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}) \\
 &= \int_{2\pi}^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{-\sin(2\pi - \theta_p) d\theta_p d\phi_p}{2} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}) \\
 &= - \int_\pi^0 \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\sin \theta_p d\theta_p d\phi_p}{2} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}). \quad (E3)
 \end{aligned}$$

This implies that we can rewrite the cost function as

$$S(\vec{\theta}) = - \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{|\sin \theta_p| d\theta_p d\phi_p}{4} \frac{d\phi_p}{2\pi} P_1(\theta_p, \phi_p, \vec{\theta}). \quad (E4)$$

Since both $g(\theta_p) = \frac{|\sin \theta_p|}{4}$ and $h(\phi) = \frac{1}{2\pi}$ are even functions, we can calculate the coefficient for the corresponding parameter shift rules:

$$c_k = \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta_p \frac{|\sin \theta_p|}{4} \frac{\sin(2\theta_p) \sin(\theta_p)}{\cos(\frac{k\pi}{2}) - \cos(\theta_p)} \quad (E5)$$

$$c_0 = \frac{2}{3} \quad c_1 = -\frac{4}{3} \quad c_2 = \frac{2}{3} \quad c_3 = -\frac{4}{3}$$

$$d_k = \int_0^{2\pi} d\phi_p \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\sin(2\phi_p) \sin(\phi_p)}{\cos(\frac{k\pi}{2}) - \cos(\phi_p)} \quad (E6)$$

$$d_0 = 1 \quad d_1 = -1 \quad d_2 = 1 \quad d_3 = -1$$

giving the expression

$$S(\vec{\theta}) = - \sum_{h=0, k=0}^{3,3} \frac{(-1)^{h+k} c_h, d_k}{16} P_1\left(\frac{h\pi}{2}, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right). \quad (E7)$$

This expression requires 16 function evaluations. However, it is possible to use the symmetries of the probability function to reduce the number of evaluations. In particular,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S(\vec{\theta}) &= - \left[\frac{1}{24} \sum_{k=0}^3 P_1\left(0, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right) + \frac{1}{12} \sum_{k=0}^3 P_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{24} \sum_{k=0}^3 P_1\left(\pi, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right) + \frac{1}{12} \sum_{k=0}^3 P_1\left(\frac{3\pi}{2}, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right) \right] \\
 &= - \left[\frac{1}{6} P_1(0, 0, \vec{\theta}) + \frac{1}{6} \sum_{k=0}^3 P_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{k\pi}{2}, \vec{\theta}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{6} P_1(\pi, 0, \vec{\theta}) \right], \quad (E8)
 \end{aligned}$$

giving the final result present in the main text.

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